

STUDIES ON THE DICHOISM OF VANADYL COMPOUNDS
PART I. MEASUREMENT OF ROTATORY DISPERSION AND
AND CIRCULAR DICHOISM OF AMMONIUM
VANADYL TARTRATES

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The rotatory dispersion and circular dichroism of ammonium vanadyl tartrates have been studied.

In a previous publication (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 57) it has been shown that a photocatalytic dichroic system for visible radiations can be obtained by reducing in ordinary light a mixture of sodium vanadate and excess of *d*-tartaric acid. The circular dichroism and optical activity are due to the fact that a violet coloured solution is obtained when the pentavalent vanadium (V^5) is reduced to the quadrivalent-stage (V^4) by excess of tartaric acid. But the exact nature of the complex formed between vanadium and tartaric acid was not studied. In this communication the actual complex has been isolated and some of its properties including rotatory dispersion and circular dichroism have also been studied.

Preparation of Ammonium Vanadyl Tartrates.—The salt was prepared by the method of Rosenheim and Mong (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1945, 148, 31). Ammonium metavanadate (NH_4)VO₃ (10g.) was suspended in water and boiled with hydrobromic acid when a deep blue solution was obtained. The solution was then evaporated to a small volume and 12 g. of *d*-tartaric acid were added. To prepare the ammonium salt, the solution was then treated with strong ammonia until it was neutralised. The solution became violet showing the formation of the complex. On cooling it in ice-cold water, fine crystals were separated. It was then filtered and washed thoroughly with ice-cold water and dried over calcium chloride in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide in a vacuum desiccator. To obtain the pure product it was recrystallised several times from distilled water and preserved in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The molecular formula of the complex as given by Rosenheim is

where R = (NH₄), Na, K, etc.

Measurement of Circular Dichroism.—Circular dichroism was measured by means of the Bruhat's apparatus which has an observational error ± 0.02 (*Bull. soc. chem.*, 1930, 47, 251). Extinction coefficient was determined by means of König-Martens spectrophotometer in an air-tight small rectangular cell of 5 mm. thickness. The solution of the substance of known strength was made in distilled water and preserved in a Thunberg tube, the last traces of oxygen being removed by washing the tube with carbon dioxide several times. The measurement of circular dichroism was carried out in a Baly's tube. The end plates of the tube was entirely free from ellipticities. The light source was a point-o'rite lamp of 1000 c.p. and monochromatic radiations were obtained by

passing the light through a monochromator. The circular dichroism has been expressed as anisotropy factor g , where $g = \frac{\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r}{\epsilon}$ in which ϵ_l , ϵ_r , and ϵ are the molecular extinction coefficients for the left circularly polarised light, right circularly polarised light and ordinary plane polarised light respectively.

$$\text{Now } \epsilon_l - \epsilon_r = \frac{4\phi}{c l} \log_{10} c \text{ and } \epsilon = \frac{2(\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1)}{c l}$$

where ϕ is the ellipticity expressed in radians, c is the molecular concentration, l is the length of the column of solution; θ_1 , and θ_2 are the spectrophotometer readings.

If c is expressed in degrees we have

$$g = \frac{4 \times 22 \times 0.4343\phi}{7 \times 180 \times c \times l} \times \frac{c \times l}{2(\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1)}$$

$$= \frac{4 \times 22 \times 0.4343 \times \phi}{7 \times 180 \times 2 (\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1)}$$

The results of the rotatory dispersion and circular dichroism are given below.

TABLE I

Conc. of Am. vanadate = $M/10$
 $\rho_H = 4.2$. Temp = 28.9° . $l = 5$ mm.

λ	Rotation	Ellipticity	$(\log \tan \theta_2 - \log \tan \theta_1)$ ($l = 5$ mm.)	g .
6500 Å	+1'05	-1'13	0'4082	-0'04189
6438	+1'11	-1'40	0'4313	-0'04922
6300	+1'79	-1'47	0'4436	-0'05025
6000	+2'43	-1'16	0'3986	-0'04431
5900	+3'00	-0'82	0'3413	-0'02755
5760	+3'22	-0'17	0'2928	-0'008304
5680	+3'52	+0'38	0'3118	+0'01848
5560	+3'52	+1'23	0'4158	+0'04451
5500	+3'40	+1'27	0'4158	+0'04634
5461	+3'26	+1'58	0'4630	+0'05176
5360	+2'76	+2'23	0'5719	+0'05754
5300	+2'10	+2'47	0'6032	+0'06212
5200	+1'35	+2'63	0'6366	+0'06266
5000	+0'18	+3'70	0'6725	+0'06059
4918	+0'05	+3'53	0'6198	+0'05188
4800	+0'08	+1'65	0'4982	+0'05128